

**PHARMACOLOGY AND IT'S ADVERSE REACTIONS OF
IMMUNETHERAPY DRUGS IN ONCOLOGY**

Lella Janaki*, Nali Mallikarjuna Rao, Kasa Aswini, Jonnalagadda Pravallika,
Maradani Sirisha

Department of Pharmacy, SIMS College of Pharmacy, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh,
522001.

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Corresponding Author*Lella Janaki**

Department of Pharmacy, SIMS
College of Pharmacy, Guntur District,
Andhra Pradesh, 522001.

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ABSTRACT

Immunotherapy is one of the most advanced cancer treatments that uses the body's own immune system to recognize and destroy cancer cells. It mainly works by blocking immune checkpoints such as PD-1, PD-L1, and CTLA-4, which are used by tumor cells to break immune attack.^[1,2,3] Some drugs like nivolumab, pembrolizumab and ipilimumab are monoclonal antibodies that improve immune cell activation and survival.^[4,7] These drugs show long-lasting results because they activate memory T-cells that continue to fight cancer even after treatment stops. However, excessive immune activation can cause side effects called immune-related adverse reactions (irAEs), which affect various organs such as the skin, lungs, intestines, liver, and endocrine glands.^[5,9,10,13] These reactions differ from normal chemotherapy side effects because they are autoimmune in nature. Most can be controlled by steroids or temporarily stopping therapy.^[6,11] This review clearly explains

the pharmacology, mechanisms, and types of adverse effects related to immunotherapy, along with steps to manage them efficiently. It also highlights the importance of pharmacovigilance and patient monitoring to make cancer immunotherapy safer and more successful in the future.^[8,15]

KEYWORDS: Immunotherapy, Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors, Pharmacology, PD-1, CTLA-4, Adverse Drug Reactions, Pharmacovigilance, Cancer Immunology, Immune

Toxicity.

INTRODUCTION

1. OVERVIEW OF IMMUNETHERAPY

Immunotherapy helps immune system to recognize and kill cancer cells. Tumor cells often block immune responses using ‘checkpoints’ like PD-L1 or CTLA-4, which act as brakes on T-cells. Checkpoint inhibitor drugs release these brakes, allowing the immune system to attack the tumor.^[1,3,4] The first approved drug, ipilimumab, showed great success in melanoma, followed by PD-1 inhibitors like nivolumab and pembrolizumab for lung, bladder, and kidney cancers.^[12]

2. PHARMACOLOGY OF IMMUNE CHECKPOINT INHIBITORS

Immune checkpoint inhibitors are large protein molecules called monoclonal antibodies. They are given by IV infusion and work by binding to specific receptors on T-cells or cancer cells.

Mechanism of Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors

Ipilimumab (CTLA-4 blocker): Acts early during T-cell activation in lymph nodes.
 Nivolumab and Pembrolizumab (PD-1 blockers): Reactivate exhausted T-cells near tumors.
 Atezolizumab and Durvalumab (PD-L1 blockers): Stop tumor cells from sending ‘don’t kill me’ signals to immune cells.^[2,5,6]

These drugs are slowly absorbed, have a long half-life (2–4 weeks), and are broken down into amino acids by body proteins instead of being metabolized by liver.^[12] Their pharmacological

effect can continue for months because they create immune memory that keeps attacking the tumor even after stopping treatment.^[3,7]

3. IMMUNE- RELATED ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS (irAEs)

Because these drugs activate the immune system, they can cause the immune cells to attack normal organs. These adverse effects are known as immune-related adverse reactions. They can appear during treatment or even several months after therapy ends.^[9,10,13]

COMMON ORGAN SYSTEM AND THEIR SYMPTOMS

System Affected	Common ADR's	Clinical symptoms	Management
Skin	Rash, pruritus, vitiligo	Itching, redness	Topical steroids, antihistamines
Gastrointestinal (GI)	Colitis, diarrhea	Abdominal pain, blood in stool	Corticosteroids, hydration
Lungs	Pneumonitis	Cough, shortness of breath	Stop Drug, give steroids
Liver	Hepatitis	Fatigue, jaundice, raised liver enzymes	Corticosteroids
Endocrine glands	Thyroiditis, adrenalitis, hypophysitis	Weight change, fatigue	Hormone replacement
Musculoskeletal	Myalgia, arthritis	Joint pain, weakness	NSAIDs, steroids

4. CLASSIFICATION OF IMMUNE-RELATED ADR's BY SEVERITY

Grade	Description	Action
Grade (mild)	Mild symptoms; continue therapy with close watch	Continue drug; supportive care
Grade 2 (Moderate)	Noticeable symptoms affecting daily life	Temporarily hold drug; start low -dose steroids
Grade 3 (severe)	Serious organ inflammation	Stop drug; start high-dose corticosteroids
Grade 4 (life-threatening)	Organ failure or severe reaction	Permanently stop drug; emergency care

FLOW CHART: STEPS IN ADR MANAGEMENT DURING IMMUNETHERAPY

5. IMPORTANCE OF PHARMCOVILIGINACE

Pharmacovigilance helps in the continuous monitoring and reporting of ADRs. Since immune-related ADRs are sometimes delayed or unpredictable, it is essential to document every reaction carefully.^[8,10] Indian systems like PvPI (Pharmacovigilance Programme of India) and global systems like WHO-UMC help collect safety data from hospitals and research centers.^[15] This data helps in updating treatment protocols and avoiding serious toxicities.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

In future cancer care focuses on combining immunotherapy with targeted therapy, vaccines, and gene therapy. Scientists are also studying biomarkers like PD-L1 levels and tumor mutational burden (TMB) to predict who will respond best to treatment.^[12,15] Artificial intelligence may soon help in predicting ADRs even before therapy starts. Personalized immunotherapy, guided by genetic tests, will make treatment safe and more effective. Pharmacists continues as an important role in patient education and monitoring.

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CONCLUSION

Immunotherapy is now a mainstay in cancer treatment, offering long-lasting results by stimulating the immune system to target cancer cells. Its pharmacology is based on blocking checkpoint pathways like PD-1, PD-L1, and CTLA-4, allowing T-cells to kill tumor cells effectively.^[1-4,7] Though, activating the immune system can lead to immune-related adverse reactions affecting many body systems.^[2,5,6,9,10] These ADRs are unique because they arise from immune overactivity, not drug toxicity. Proper recognition and management are key to preventing complications. Pharmacovigilance programs help track these ADRs and improve patient safety.^[8,11,15] Doctors usually treat side effects with corticosteroids and temporary drug suspension. Most patients recover well if managed early. The future of immunotherapy will focus on accurate medicine, biomarker discovery and AI-based monitoring systems.^[12,15] By understanding its pharmacology and adverse reactions, pharmacists and clinicians can ensure that these drugs used safely and effectively. Immunotherapy has truly transformed oncology by turning cancer into a treatable and controllable disease, offering new hope for patients around the world.

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